

Object Detection and Segmentation for Autonomous Vehicles

A Comparative Study of YOLOv8, Mask R-CNN, and DeepLabv3

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July, 2025

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1. Introduction

1.1 Autonomous Vehicles

Autonomous vehicles, also called self-driving cars, are vehicles that do not require a human to drive. These vehicles are self-driven, hence the name, self-driving.

The need for object detection in autonomous vehicles is so important as it uses semantic segmentation and other machine learning technologies to recognize living and non-living objects on the road.

Hence, preventing accidents, mistakes, and wrong driving. Plus, it reduces the risk that is associated with self-driving vehicles.

1.2 Objectives of Object Detection in Autonomous Vehicles

“Autonomous driving is a big challenge for next-generation **vehicles** and requires multiple computationally-intensive deep neural networks (DNNs) to be implemented on distributed automotive platforms.” (Devulapalli et al., 2023, p.1).

(Xiaozhi et al., 2016) stated that many of the recent object detection pipelines typically proceed by generating a diverse set of object proposals that have a high recall and are relatively fast to compute. “Multi-task learning (MTL) is one of the most well-known techniques for simultaneously dealing with multiple tasks, which can exploit the shared information of multiple related tasks and improve the performance of each other. This statement has been proven both empirically and theoretically”. (Yaran et al., 2017, p.25)

1.3 Overview of Object Detection in Autonomous Vehicles

Even though a lot of work has been done to improve object detection for vehicles, more research and machine-learning technologies are being used and developed for this purpose.

A large list of technologies like YOLO versions, Retina net, multispectral, U-net, and a lot more technologies aid object detection.

The principle of object detection is built on object segmentation, which is divided into instance segmentation and semantic segmentation.

However, semantic segmentation is mostly used to detect and group similar objects with similar models, hence, detecting living from non-living objects on the road.

Instance segmentation is still used for deeper analysis.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Technologies Used in Object Detection

“3D object detection at long range is crucial for ensuring the safety and efficiency of self-driving vehicles, allowing them to accurately perceive and react to objects, obstacles, and potential hazards from a distance.” (Ajhinkya et al., 2024, p.1).

Technologies used for computer vision object detection are extensive and have, over the years, improved, increased, and expanded their data collection and usage.

Some of the technologies which this report will be based on are

- **YOLO (You Only Look Once)**

YOLO has many versions like YOLOn, YOLO5, YOLO8, YOLOI, and many more. It. (Aduen et al., 2023, p.2) explains how detecting small objects in images can be challenging, mainly due to limited resolution and context information available to a model, which happens to be in their numbers.

The latest, YOLO8, comes with add-ons, improvements, and adjustments. It helps with real-time object detection to enable increased speed and accuracy.

- **R-CNN Family**

which is divided into fast RCNN and faster RCNN. Faster R-CNN helps with high-precision object detection. The term R-CNN means region-based convolutional

neural network. Therefore emphasizes its importance in object detection for autonomous vehicles.

- Another one in this category is the Mask R-CNN, which is quite similar to faster R-CNN, but it aids with a more advanced form of object detection that requires boundary detection and deeper analysis.
- **DeepLabv3**
- Used for semantic segmentation
- Suitable for class-based segmentation but lacks precision for individual object boundaries

3. Methodology and Models

3.1 Models Used

“As a family of object detectors, YOLO takes this idea further and has grown very popular over the last few years. With YOLOv1, object detection is presented as a regression task, thus simplifying the networks and allowing us to build faster models that can be used in real time. Later versions of YOLO improve different aspects of the model. Most notably, much effort has been spent on the backbone through the different versions. This begs the question: What potential is there still untapped if changes to an isolated element can have such an impact?”. (Aduen et al., 2024, p.33).

3.2 State of the Art object detection and segmentation models

YOLOv8

Model Type: Real-time object detection

Advantages and Pros: It is fast, and it has good accuracy

Disadvantages and Cons: Tends to misclassify images

Mask R-CNN

Model Type: Instance Segmentation

Advantages and Pros: It is more precise and can give precise segmentation of individual

Disadvantages and Pros: It is slower to process

DeepLabv3

Model Type: Semantic Segmentation

Advantages and Pros: It is good for segmenting classes and objects

Disadvantages and cons: it is not very precise for individual object boundaries

3.3 Evaluation and Implementation

Here, various technologies and pipelines were used to bring this to life

1. **Python** programming language
2. **Libraries** used include: openCv, PyTorch, detectron2, ultralytics

3.4 Steps taken to achieve adequate results

1. Firstly, load the input video by adding the needed video to the directory
2. Write the code for object detection for each of the models in different files
3. Apply object detection and segmentation using each model
4. Run your code and analyze the video output
5. Annotate video frames
6. Save and repeat this process for each model
7. Afterwards, compare all three outputs

3.5 Evaluation and Comparison

Model	Accuracy	Processing Speed	Pros	Cons
YOLOv8	High	Fastest	Real-time	May misclassify

			detection, Best for real-time use	objects, and may also miss small objects
Mask R-CNN	Very High	Slower	Precise instance segmentation, Excellent accuracy	It has slower inference and it is not real-time
DeepLabV3	High	Moderate	Good for semantic segmentation. pixel-wise segmentation	Less precise for individual objects

4. Results and Output

4.1 Sample Frames from each model

YOLOv8

Mask R-CNN

DeepLabv3

4.2 Processed Video Results

DeepLabv3 Output: 📺 output_deeplab.mp4

Mask R-CNN Output: 📺 output_maskrcnn.mp4

YOLOv8 Output: 📺 output_yolo.mp4

Key Challenges and Limitations faced in the process.

5. Conclusion and Best Model Selection

5.1 Summary of Findings:

- YOLOv8 is best for real-time applications.
- Mask R-CNN is best for detailed segmentation.
- DeepLabV3 is best for general semantic segmentation.

5.2 Best Model for the Task: From my research and analysis, Mask R-CNN has the best model result, followed by YOLOv8, then lastly, Mask R-CNN

5.3 Improvements to be done:

- Although the current models used work, combining models can enhance accuracy. Seeing that Mask R-CNN is more accurate but slower, combining it with YOLOv8 and deepLabv3 will give a much better result.
- With more custom training, these models will be improved and hence, improve detection performance.
- Also, by optimizing inference speed for real-time applications, we can get better results

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